

A respectable lady who inspired my PhD thesis

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Abstract: This manuscript describes how my PhD thesis was inspired by Dr. Nina F. Thornhill's research work on causality analysis especially on the transfer entropy approach. She provided me with a lot of helpful comments to improve the quality of my papers and my PhD thesis. Besides, her one action – jumping onto a desk to turn on projector in our meeting room, influenced my personal development as well. I would like to express my gratitude to this respectable lady, and wish her a wonderful and colorful retirement life.

Keywords: Causality analysis, Transfer Entropy, Jumping onto a desk.

1. INTRODUCED BY DR. SIRISH SHAH

I began my PhD program at University of Alberta in Sep 2009. After I finished my courses in 2010, I started to work on data-based causality analysis for capturing cause and effect relationship between process variables. My supervisor Dr. Sirish Shah suggested me to looking into Dr. Nina F. Thornhill's research work on causality analysis. I read through her co-authored paper "Finding the Direction of Disturbance Propagation in a Chemical Process Using Transfer Entropy" published on *IEEE Transactions on Control Systems Technology* in Feb 2007. This paper demonstrated how the transfer entropy method works for causality analysis and inspired me how to continue my research work based on the transfer entropy method.

2. MEETING WITH DR. NINA THORNHILL

Inspired by Dr. Thornhill's research work on causality analysis, I proposed a direct causality detection method based on the transfer entropy method.

On April 24, 2012, Dr. Thornhill visited the University of Alberta. My supervisor Dr. Shah scheduled a meeting for me to give a presentation to her and discuss about if my results are of interest to her and worth publishing.

At 4 pm that day, we went to the meeting room ECERF W2-058 at University of Alberta. I was trying to turn on the projector. After I pressed the power button on the remote controller, the projector did not give us any response. Obviously, I had a trouble to turn it on. Suddenly Dr. Thornhill jumped onto the table under the projector and manually turned the projector on! At that moment I was a little bit shocked. I had to admit that she is much more active than me, and she is awesome!

After I gave a presentation, she encouraged me to publish my work. She also provided me with some comments. Until now, I still remember one comment was to add a causal map to

better illustrate the causality relationships between process variables, which made my results more readable and understandable. Besides, she recommended two references to me.

With her helpful comments, our paper "Direct Causality Detection via the Transfer Entropy Approach" was accepted and published by *IEEE Transactions on Control Systems Technology* as a regular paper in 2013.

3. CONCLUSIONS

Besides the causality analysis, our survey paper "Methods for detection and root cause diagnosis of plant-wide oscillations" published on *AIChE* was also inspired by Dr. Thornhill's research work. I would like to use this opportunity to extend my sincere thanks to her and her research group.

As a conclusion, I would like to quote my words in the "Acknowledgements" section of my PhD thesis:

"My earnest thanks to Dr. Nina F. Thornhill from Imperial College London, UK, for comments and suggestions on direct causality analysis."

With my Best Wishes to Dr. Nina F. Thornhill! I wish that you would have a wonderful and colourful retirement life!

REFERENCES

- P. Duan, F. Yang, T. Chen, and S.L. Shah (2013). Direct causality detection via the transfer entropy approach. *IEEE Transactions on Control Systems Technology*, 21 (6), 2052–2066.
- M. Bauer, J.W. Cox, M.H. Caveness, J.J. Downs, and N.F. Thornhill (2007). Finding the direction of disturbance propagation in a chemical process using transfer entropy. *IEEE Transactions on Control Systems Technology*, 15 (1), 12–21.

- P. Duan, S.L. Shah, T. Chen, and F. Yang (2014). Methods for root cause diagnosis of plant-wide oscillations. *AIChE Journal*, 60 (6).
- P. Duan (2014). Information Theory-based Approaches for Causality Analysis with Industrial Applications. *PhD Thesis*, University of Alberta.